

Implementation of adapted volume distribution in the basic dynamic Hickling Model

J. Hofman¹, J. Bamboschek¹, N. Fix¹, K. Möller¹

¹ Institute of Technical Medicine, Furtwangen University, Villingen-Schwenningen, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: knut.moeller@hs-furtwangen.de

Accurate modeling of lung dynamics is crucial for understanding respiratory physiology and developing effective treatments. This study extends the basic dynamic Hickling model by introducing an adapted volume distribution, resulting in a more accurate simulation of lung mechanics. The incorporation of adapted volume distribution improves the model's ability to simulate dynamic pressure changes during mechanical ventilation and addresses the overestimation of end-inspiratory pressure. Compared to the basic model, the enhanced version demonstrates significant improvements in representing physiological behavior.

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I. Introduction

In respiratory physiology, modeling of the lung's dynamic behavior is essential for understanding various non-linear aspects of lung function and developing effective treatments [1]. The Hickling model is a well-established approach that simulates lung mechanics by considering the behavior of individual alveolar units, grouped in layers [1]. This project aims to extend the basic dynamic Hickling model by introducing the effect of changing compliance on the resulting pressure through the implementation of adapted volume distribution. In the original dynamic Hickling model, the formula for calculating pressure could not account for a reduction in pressure once compliance increased due to alveolar recruitment. Since the pressure could only increase, this led to an incorrect high end-inspiratory pressure. By adapting volume distribution when recruitment happens i.e. layers open, the corrected model aims to provide a more comprehensive representation of lung dynamics, potentially offering valuable insights for preclinical and clinical applications.

II. Material and methods

The basic dynamic Hickling model used in this article is described with the following system of ordinary differential equations (ODE) [1]:

$$\dot{p}_a = \frac{\dot{V}}{C_{FRC}e^{-Kp_a} + C_L \sum_n^1 (H_n e^{p_a - SP_n - TOP})} \quad (1)$$

$$p_{aw} = R_{PRM} \dot{V} + p_a \quad (2)$$

The opening of a layer is governed by a Heaviside function, which compares the pressure p_a with the threshold pressure ($SP_n + TOP$) required to open a specific layer. The Heaviside function is described as [1]:

$$H_n = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-2(p_a - SP_n - TOP)}} \quad (3)$$

In this research, Euler integration was employed to solve the system of ordinary differential equations. Euler integration, an explicit numerical method, approximates

solutions by incrementally advancing steps (h), utilizing the derivative at the current point to estimate subsequent points [2]. It can be mathematically expressed as [2]:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(t_n, y_n) \quad (4)$$

This method was selected due to its capability to control all variables involved in solving the ODE, thereby allowing adjustments to the current point on which the subsequent step is approximated.

Equation 1 was implemented in MATLAB and solved using the following formulation:

$$p_a(i) = p_a(i-1) + \dot{p}_a \cdot h \quad (5)$$

The reduction in pressure due to changes in compliance was modeled through an adopted volume distribution. To account for this, the current pressure ($p_a(i-1)$) was adjusted upon the opening of a new layer, using equation 6:

$$p_a(i-1) = \frac{V(i)}{C_{New}} \quad (6)$$

The new compliance, C_{New} , was derived from equation 1. As layers opened, compliance increased, leading to a decrease in pressure, which was then used for subsequent iterations. The volume $V(i)$ was calculated by integrating the volume over time using equation 7:

$$V(i) = V(i-1) + \dot{V} \cdot h \quad (7)$$

After a certain period of inspiration (T_{End}), an end-inspiratory pause (EIP) was incorporated into the model, by setting $\dot{V} = 0$.

Following the implementation of the model, a comparative analysis was performed between the basic dynamic Hickling Model and the model incorporating the adapted volume distribution. Furthermore, an investigation into the accumulation error was conducted.

III. Results and discussion

The modified Hickling model, and the standard dynamic Hickling Model were implemented in MATLAB and solved using Euler Integration, by using the following Input values:

R [mbar s/ml]	C [ml/mbar]	Layers [-]	TOP [-]	\dot{V} [ml/s]	K [-]
0.0722	72.22	4	5	500	0.0018

Table 1: Input values for the dynamic Hickling model as identified by Docherty et al. [3].

Figure 1 presents a dynamic Hickling model, consisting of 4 layers, to better illustrate the effects of pressure compensation due to compliance changes. The EIP starts after 3.5 seconds. The initial pressure for p_a was set to 0 mbar, with an observed offset of approximately 37 mbar as described by Equation 2. Fluctuations during rise time can be attributed to the opening of alveolar layers, which increases compliance and consequently decreases pressure.

Figure 2: Comparison of dynamic Hickling Model with and without adapted volume distribution

The pressure drop observed is due to the opening of alveolar layers, leading to a difference in plateau pressures. This pressure difference represents the accumulation of error with each new layer that opens. Figure 2 demonstrates the accumulation of error with varying tidal volumes (V_T). The first graph depicts an EIP at 1.5 seconds, yielding a V_T of 750 ml with a set flow rate of 500 ml/s. The difference between the two plateau pressures, denoted as Δ_1 , has a magnitude of 3.19 mbar. The second graph shows an EIP at 4.5 seconds with a V_T of 2250 ml at a flow rate of 500 ml/s. Although this value is not physiologically accurate and does not align with lung-protective ventilation strategies [4], it was selected to illustrate the increased accumulation of error. The magnitude of Δ_2 , at 5.79 mbar, which is reached after about 3 seconds, indicates that Δ increases with larger V_T , because the recruited volume is increasing, leading to accumulated errors in the basic dynamic Hickling model. The implementation of adapted volume distribution showed significant improvements over the basic dynamic Hickling model. This is evidenced by the lower plateau pressures observed, indicating that the model can effectively account for the dynamic changes in lung

Figure 1: Accumulation of error with different V_T ($\Delta_1 = 3.19$ mbar, $\Delta_2 = 5.79$ mbar)

compliance as alveolar units open. Therefore, providing a more realistic simulation of respiratory mechanics.

The model used in this research cannot be solved using common Runge-Kutta solvers, such as the ode-family in MATLAB, because it requires an adjustment of pressure before each iteration. A potential direction for future research is to develop a method to incorporate the pressure correction described in this article into a system of ordinary differential equations, making it solvable by Runge-Kutta solvers. Additionally, validating the simulated values of the model using clinical measurements could be another area for further investigation.

IV. Conclusions

Extending the basic dynamic Hickling model by introducing an adapted volume distribution provides a more accurate approximation of the lung's physiological behavior. This enhanced model more effectively represents the dynamic pressure changes during mechanical ventilation, addressing the issue of overestimating end-inspiratory pressure and offering a more correct simulation of lung mechanics.

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AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

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